

FINAL PROJECT REPORT

1 General information

DFG reference number: KL 3646/1-1

Project number: 521902629

Project title:

German: Formbarkeit von stark vernetzten Polymeren – eine Untersuchung des topologischen Einfrierprozesses von Vitrimern auf Basis statischer und dynamischer Methoden und dessen Relevanz für die Lösung technischer Herausforderungen

English: Malleability of highly cross-linked polymers – an investigation of the topology freezing phenomenon of Vitrimers via static and dynamic means and its relevance for the solution of technological challenges

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2 Summary

German:

Das Walter-Benjamin Projekt beschäftigte sich im Zeitraum Mai 2023 bis April 2025 mit grundlegenden Fragestellungen zu einer relativ neuen Polymerklasse, sogenannten *Vitrimeren*. Vitrimere kombinieren makroskopisch die Hochtemperatur-*Fließfähigkeit* von Thermoplasten mit den ausgezeichneten mechanischen Eigenschaften von molekular stark vernetzten Duroplasten. Durch eine besondere molekulare Bindungsdynamik, dem sogenannten assoziativ kovalenten dynamischen Bindungsaustausch, sind Vitrimere in der Lage, trotz ihres molekularvernetzten Zustands, der durch einen Polymerisationsvorgang erzeugt wird, jenseits der Perkolationgrenze, temperaturabhängig repariert, umgeformt und recycelt zu werden ohne ihre Strukturintegrität zu verlieren. Diese Kombination, dieser bis dato nicht kombinierbaren makroskopischen Eigenschaftsprofile ermöglicht so ganz neue Perspektiven für den zukünftigen nachhaltigen Einsatz von Polymerwerkstoffen, z.B. durch die Heilung von Defekten.

Ursächlich motiviert durch die in der Fachliteratur aufgestellte Behauptung, dass dieser neue, fließfähige Hochtemperaturzustand durch einen ungewöhnlichen zusätzlichen Glasübergang beim Abkühlen zum duroplastischen Zustand bei einer Temperatur T_v , neben dem kanonischen Glasübergang bei $T_g < T_v$ getrennt wäre, war es das Ziel des Projekts ein besseres, physikalisch-technisches Verständnis der zugrundeliegenden Mechanismen von Vitrimeren zu erarbeiten und das Vitrimereübergangsverhalten (vom fließfähigen Zustand zum duroplastischen Zustand) besser zu verstehen.

Im Rahmen des Walter-Benjamin-Projekts war es möglich zu zeigen, dass sich auf Basis von ausgewählten Vitrimere-Modellsystemen und der Kombination von verschiedenen thermischen und thermo-optischen Analysemethoden, im Bereich der linearen Antworttheorie, keine Hinweise auf einen zusätzlichen Übergang $T_v > T_g$ zeigten. Erst durch zusätzliche Störgrößen, wie eine äußere Kraft, konnten Anomalien, z.B. in der thermischen Dehnung, beobachtet werden, die vermutlich auf nicht-lineares Antwortverhalten zurückzuführen sind. Der fließfähig-fest Übergang passt nicht in die klassischen Konzepte von Phasen- und Glasübergängen. Stattdessen spielen die spezielle Bindungsdynamik der Vitrimere und Nichtlinearitäten eine Rolle, die möglicherweise mit einem im Rahmen des Projekts vorgeschlagenen neuen Übergangskonzept in Zusammenhang stehen: einem dynamischen De- und Re-Perkulationsübergang. Technologisch betrachtet, hat sich die Annahme verfestigt, dass der temperaturabhängige Transformationsprozess von Vitrimeren, vom fließfähigen zum festen Zustand, rein operativer Natur ist und der kanonische Glasübergang bei T_g das Fließvermögen von Vitrimeren beendet.

English:

The Walter Benjamin project (May 2023 – April 2025) focused on fundamental questions about vitrimers, a relatively new class of polymers. Vitrimers combine at the macroscopic level, the high-temperature flowability of thermoplastics with the outstanding mechanical performance of highly crosslinked thermosets. Due to their special molecular bond dynamics, an associative covalent dynamic bond exchange process, they can, despite being permanently crosslinked, temperature-dependently still be repaired, reshaped, and recycled without losing their structural integrity. This unique property profile, combining features previously thought to be incompatible, opens up new and sustainable opportunities for polymer and polymer composite applications.

The project was originally motivated by a claim in literature that this flowable high-temperature phase is separated from the thermoset state by an unusual additional glass transition at T_v , in addition to the canonical glass transition at $T_g < T_v$. Inspired by this unusual thought, the project aimed to develop a more profound physico-technical understanding of the underlying mechanisms of vitrimers and to elucidate the vitrimer transition behavior (from the flowable to the thermoset state).

Within the framework of the Walter Benjamin project, it was demonstrated, based on selected vitrimer model systems and by combining various thermal and thermo-optical analytical methods, that no indications of an additional transition $T_v > T_g$ could be observed under linear response conditions. Only under the influence of additional perturbations, such as an external force, temperature-dependent investigations of vitrimers revealed additional anomalies, e.g., in the thermal expansion behavior. It was found that the transition from the flowable to the thermoset state does not fit into classical concepts of phase or glass transitions. Instead, the bond exchange dynamics of vitrimers and nonlinearities play a key role, which may be associated with a new transition concept proposed within the framework of the project: a dynamic de- and re-percolation transition. Nevertheless, from a technological standpoint, the current understanding of vitrimers and their underlying dynamics reinforce the idea that the vitrimer transition from flowable to solid is purely operational, with the canonical glass transition ultimately ending vitrimer flowability.

3 Scientific Progress Report

Background and Objectives:

Vitrimers are a rather novel class of dynamic polymer networks which, depending on the temperature, either exist in a cross-linked thermoset state or a flowable state [1,2]. In other words, they are amorphous, thermally-controlled, two-phase systems. This dual behaviour, the coexistence of a low temperature *thermoset* phase that usually shows temperature *independently* eternal characteristics and the flowable high temperature phase, is highly unusual and necessitates a

special transformation mechanism. This mechanism is governed by a dynamic molecular process referred to in the literature as *associative dynamic molecular bond exchange mechanism* (DMBE-mechanism) [3]. It allows vitrimers to prevail their cross-link density while undergoing macroscopic flow.

Besides the fascinating possibilities to repair and reshape actually cross-linked polymers beyond classical rubber-elasticity, the central question in this Walter Benjamin project was how the transition from the flowable to the thermoset state (and vice versa) takes place: (i) fully continuous or via a (phase) transition phenomenon, i.e., spontaneous (ii) or even cooperatively (iii) at a certain transition temperature T_v ? If these two states, the flowable-phase and the thermoset-phase are thermodynamically stable, i.e., if they form indeed thermodynamic phases, then both phases should be separated by a phase transition [4]. Due to the macroscopic isotropy of both phases, this transition should then also be isostructural in nature. The above question is not only driven by pure scientific curiosity, but also by its engineering relevance to design polymer (composite) properties. The literature discusses mostly a transformation scenario in the sense of a *glass transition* at a transition temperature T_v [1,5]. This *additional* glass transition at T_v is classified as a “strong glass former” [1,6], whereas in the thermoset temperature range, the canonical glass transition T_g takes place as usual.

The main goal of the Walter Benjamin research project was to gain a better understanding of the vitrimer-inherent malleability/flowability by investigating static and dynamic physical properties, such as the thermal volume expansion behaviour. To get a clearer picture of the consequences of the dynamic molecular bond exchange process on the continuum properties of vitrimers, the idea was to probe static, dynamic and kinetic aspects of the flowability of vitrimers, foremost with a variety of measuring techniques that are especially versatile to probe these properties in broad frequency, time and temperature intervals.

Description of the project-specific results and findings:

The topology freezing process and its coupling to the canonical glass transition:

The initial assumption was, if vitrimers indeed flow [1], and upon cooling static shear stiffness sets on at $T > T_g$ and the material gains a viscoelastic solid character, then these thermodynamically stable *phases* have to be separated by a phase transition, which should be accessible via the (dynamic) thermal volume expansion, due to a coupling to the average anharmonic molecular interaction potential [7]. Using the rather new technique of temperature-modulated optical refractometry (TMOR) [8] in combination with thermo-mechanical analysis (TMA) [9], it is shown in Ref. [10] that the vitrimer transition phenomenon seemingly appears indeed as an anomaly in *biased*

thermal volume expansion data, if a force is applied during the measurements (probed via TMA), cf. Fig. 1.

FIG 1. Dynamic thermal volume expansion β' and dynamic pseudo-thermal volume expansion γ of DGEBA/Pripol1040/TBD-10mol% measured via TMOR and TMA, respectively. The TMOR data was obtained force-free at $f = 1.7$ mHz. TMA experiments were performed using a constant probing force of $F = 0.1$ N. Data adapted from Ref. [10]

On the other hand, in force-free TMOR measurements, no indication for a vitrimer transition is found. Additionally, reducing the cooling-rate during TMA measurements allows shifting the observed anomaly, usually considered as a signal indicating the vitrimer transition, down to the canonical glass transition at T_g . The glass transition ultimately suppresses the dynamic molecular bond exchange processes. Hence, the vitrimer transition is a somewhat force-controlled phenomenon that has, from the current understanding, only an operational character but not a thermodynamic one. Interestingly, the canonical glass transition temperature did not appear to be affected by the TMA measuring conditions used in this study. A detailed investigation of the glass transition process, probed via TMOR is currently under review. A preprint of the work can be found at Ref. [11].

Building up on these findings, in the course of the project, a concept was developed that would allow the interpretation of a vitrimer transition based on a new concept, a dynamic de- and re-percolation transition, originating from the dynamic molecular bond exchange, cf. schematically Fig. 2. The concept is presented and discussed in more detail in Ref. [12].

The above mentioned force aspect is something that accompanies most of the results presented in literature on vitrimer transition phenomena, e.g. in shear relaxation experiments, in thermo-mechanical analysis or in dynamic mechanical analysis. From the current perspective, it seems like as if even minor forces, beyond gravity, induce non-linear response conditions in the vitrimer during a measurement. On the other hand, when the vitrimer transition is probed under linear

response conditions, the transition phenomenon remains hidden in the thermal volume expansion. Either, the measurements are not sensitive enough to observe changes induced by the dynamic molecular bond exchange (as suggested in Ref. [12]) or one has to deal with a highly non-linear phenomenon that would reduce most of the current measurements of the vitrimer transition phenomenon and the assigned temperature T_v to a purely operational parameter.

FIG 2. Schematic of a possible dynamic phase transition at T_v due to DMBE. Upon cooling the vitrimer from the flowable high-temperature phase to the thermoset state, triggered by the dynamic molecular bond exchange process the viscosity η diverges at T_v and the static shear stiffness G_s starts to evolve.

In this regard, a special feature in TMOR measurements has been discovered and was published in [13]. Probing the dynamic thermal volume expansion via TMOR, e.g., of the used model vitrimers, generates additional thermo-mechanical losses in β'' at $T > T_g$. These violate the Kramers-Kronig relationship [14,15] because of the actual constancy of $\beta'(T)$. This additional linear increase of $\beta''(T)$ can be interpreted as dynamically-induced (or biased) high temperature shear data, due to friction interaction between sample and prism surface of the TMOR device [13]. On the one hand, these additional shear-elastic data did not indicate the existence of an additional transformation temperature T_v ! However, there is evidence of a dynamically stimulated canonical glass transition temperature based on the convergence of all damping lines $\beta_f''(T)$ to a prominent single temperature $T_{g,TOC}$, providing a perspective on the high-temperature dynamics of the vitrimer materials that become interrupted at T_g .

In the course of the project, it was possible to collaborate with an expert on Brillouin spectroscopy (BS), Dr. *Rafael J. Jiménez Riobóo*. BS uses optical light scattering to detect longitudinal and transversal sound velocities in the hypersonic regime [16]. This allowed probing temperature-dependently elastic constants of the model vitrimer in the linear elastic regime. The following data

have not yet been published and are the first data to be reported using BS on a model vitrimer (DGEBA/Pripol1040-TBD catalysed).

Fig. 3 shows the longitudinal modulus $c_L = E$ and the hypersonic losses Γ^{180A} of DGEBA/Pripol1040/TBD-10mol%, based on temperature-jumps to gain access to temperature-equilibrated conditions of the material.

FIG 3. Longitudinal modulus c_L and the associated hypersonic losses Γ^{180A} of a model vitrimer DGEBA/Pripol1040/TBD-10mol% upon cooling by temperature jumps. The data shows the dynamic $T_{g,dyn}$ and the quasi-static glass transition $T_{g,stat}$.

The modulus shows a kink in the low temperature regime. This is interpreted as the static canonical glass transition process [17,18] at about $T_{g,stat} = -0.6^\circ\text{C}$. Most interestingly, this value corresponds perfectly to the high temperature dynamics extrapolation of DGEBA/Pripol1040/TBD measured via TMOR $T_g^{HT} \sim -1^\circ\text{C}$, reported in Ref. [13], indicating that both methods detect the same transition phenomenon. Such a correlation is only conceivable if the high-frequency-clamped hypersonic velocity detects a static anomaly of the longitudinal modulus at $T_{g,stat}$. Nevertheless, further BS and TMOR investigations are required to investigate the apparent coincidence.

Furthermore, a dynamic glass transition process about 100 K above $T_{g,stat}$, at $T_{g,dyn} = 103^\circ\text{C}$ is revealed, as a maximum in the loss curve at GHz frequencies [18,19]. In between this temperature range no further anomalies appear in the data sets that would be indicative for a vitrimer transition phenomenon and thus a transition from a flowable to a non-flowable phase state. This is a quite interesting observation, especially in the context with the inconspicuous thermal volume expansion data. If the dynamic thermal volume expansion and density fluctuations are not affected by the DMBE process, what other morphologically-related property should be? Apparently, neither thermal volume expansion nor the longitudinal elastic modulus provide us with any

immediate insight into a vitrimer transition. These results raise again the question of the influence of non-linearities, e.g., imposed via external forces on the transition behaviour of vitrimers and, in particular the T_v as shown via shear rheological measurements or thermo-mechanical analysis.

Interface-induced molecular interactions of vitrimer properties

Another aspect within the Walter Benjamin project was the question to which extent additives can modify the vitrimer properties and their temperature-dependent behaviour. Therefore, the model vitrimer DGEBA/Pripol1040/TBD-10mol% was modified using about $v_f \sim 2.7 \text{ vol. } \% \text{ Al}_2\text{O}_3$. It was found that the Al_2O_3 -nanoparticle modification of the vitrimer forms additional non-covalent bond interphases, yet these did not significantly affect the shape changing behaviour of the matrix vitrimer. The results were presented at the European Conference on Composite Materials and have been published in Ref. [20]

Imaging of transition phenomena of vitrimers via polymerization

In the course of polymerization, from the initial oligomeric state to the fully polymerized end state of a polymer, all structural changes, which lead to the different transition phenomena in the final state of a polymer sample, are passed [21,22]. Considering that there might be a pure thermal precursor for a vitrimer transition at $T_v > T_g$, the idea was that this transition has to be passed as well, during polymerisation. Using TMOR and a rigorous time- and equipment-consuming approach, it was not possible to clearly identify an anomaly that might be assigned to a vitrimer transition phenomenon. In comparison to the polymerisation process of a rather classical epoxy resin, the polymerisation process of the model vitrimer showed a type of double step polymerisation, which is temperature dependent and takes time-dependently always place, cf. Fig.4.

FIG 4. Refractive index development of the model vitrimer DGEBA/Pripol1040/TBD-10mol% at different polymerisation temperatures.

Short summary:

This Walter Benjamin project was able to demonstrate that the often thought idea of an additional glass transition process in vitrimers at $T > T_g$ needs to be refined. It was found that the transition from the flowable to the thermoset state does not fit into classical concepts of phase or glass transitions! Instead, the bond exchange dynamics of vitrimers and especially nonlinearities play a key role, which may be associated with a new transition concept proposed within the framework of the project: a dynamic de- and re-percolation transition.

Deviations from the original concept

Some minor adjustments to the original project plan had to be performed:

- Originally it was planned to use zinc acetate (Zn) as a catalyst for the vitrimer flow behaviour. Zn was right at the beginning replaced by Triazabicyclodecene (TBD) due to its more efficient catalytic effect and the easy processing of the vitrimer systems. Also, it was part of the original vitrimer study [1] and literature data was broadly available.
- After initial discussions with the advisory board, infrared spectroscopy (IR) was rejected as a primary tool to investigate the vitrimer transition phenomena. Instead, the focus was put on other techniques, such as Brillouin spectroscopy (see above).
- Force-controlled calorimetry was not performed. The limited time of the project in combination with the potential complexity of such an additional, not commercially available approach did not allow the investigation of the vitrimer transition behaviour. Nevertheless, this approach could still be a very promising aspect in the future.

Description of the handling of research data

All data generated within this project were stored in non-proprietary formats to ensure long-term accessibility. Each dataset was accompanied by a metadata file and assigned a unique UUID code, facilitating reproducibility, findability, and re-use after the end of the project. Data were stored locally during the project and regularly backed up to the IVW server infrastructure. In addition, data related to publications were deposited on the public data repository *Zenodo.org* (<https://zenodo.org/communities/dfg-wb-macrop/>), which provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) and ensures long-term archiving. Most of the scientific outputs (currently four journal articles, one book chapter, and one peer-reviewed conference proceeding) were published under open access licences (cf. Section 4). Where possible, links to the respective underlying datasets in the public repository were included, in order to support transparency, reproducibility, and re-use by the research community.

Bibliography

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications (*Chronologically sorted*)

- [A1] A. Klingler, M. Gilberg, D. Reisinger, S. Schlögl, B. Wetzel, and J.-K. Krüger, 'Thermal volume expansion as seen by Temperature-modulated optical refractometry, Oscillating dilatometry and Thermo-mechanical analysis', *Polymer Testing*, vol. 131, p. 108340, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.polymertesting.2024.108340 (**Open Access, Journal publication**).
- [A2] A. Klingler, B. Wetzel, and J.-K. Krüger, 'Temperature-Controlled Molecular Bonding Hysteresis: Interphase Dynamics of a Nanoparticle-Modified Polymer Network', *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*, pp. 3576–3580, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1021/acs.jpcclett.4c00406 (**Open Access, Journal Publication**).
- [A3] A. Klingler and J.-K. Krüger, 'The vitrimer transition phenomenon and its consequences for polymer composite materials', in *Proceedings of the 21st European Conference on Composite Materials*, Nantes Université, France, 2024. doi: 10.60691/YJ56-NP80 (**Open Access, Conference Proceedings**).
- [A4] A. Klingler, B. Wetzel, and J.-K. Krüger, 'The thermo-optical coefficient as an alternative probe for the structural arrest of polymeric glass formers', *Polymer*, vol. 298, p. 126868, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.polymer.2024.126868 (**Journal Publication**).
- [A5] A. Klingler, D. Reisinger, S. Schlögl, B. Wetzel, U. Breuer, and J.-K. Krüger, 'Vitrimer Transition Phenomena from the Perspective of Thermal Volume Expansion and Shape (In)stability', *Macromolecules*, vol. 57, no. 9, pp. 4246–4253, May 2024, doi: 10.1021/acs.macromol.4c00207 (**Open Access, Journal Publication**).
- [A6] A. Klingler and J.-K. Krüger, 'Vitrimer: new types of reshapable, repairable and recyclable polymer matrices – a physical-technical perspective', in *Multifunctionality of polymer composites*, 2nd ed., Elsevier, 2025, ISBN: 978-0-443-28873-9 (**Book chapter**).

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results

- [B1] A. Klingler, B. Wetzel, and J.-K. Krüger, 'Vitrimer Phase Transition from the perspective of ultra-slow volume changes', presented at the EUPOC 2023 - Dynamic Polymer Networks, Bertinoro, Italy, May 14, 2023 (**Conference**).
- [B2] A. Klingler and J.-K. Krüger, 'The vitrimer transition phenomenon and its consequences for polymer composite materials', presented at the European Conference on Composite Materials 21, Nantes, France, 05.07 2024 (**Conference**).

- [B3] A. Klingler, 'Simultaneous insights into the dynamic thermal volume expansion and shear relaxation behaviour of dynamic polymer networks', presented at the Dynamic Polymer Networks Meeting 2025, Reykjavik, Iceland, Aug. 13, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://dpn2025.com/> (**Conference**).
- [B4] A. Klingler, 'Data for: Thermal volume expansion as seen by Temperature-modulated optical refractometry, Oscillating dilatometry and Thermo-mechanical analysis'. Zenodo, Jan. 11, 2024. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.8424580 (**Data set**).
- [B5] A. Klingler, 'Data for: The thermo-optical coefficient as an alternative probe for the structural arrest of polymeric glass formers'. Zenodo, Feb. 29, 2024. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.10040654 (**Data set**).
- [B6] A. Klingler, 'Data for: Temperature-controlled Molecular Bonding Hysteresis: Interphase Dynamics of a Nanoparticle-modified Polymer Network'. Zenodo, Mar. 25, 2024. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.10783429 (**Data set**).
- [B7] A. Klingler, 'Data for: Vitrimer transition phenomena from the perspective of thermal volume expansion and shape (in)stability'. Zenodo, Apr. 26, 2024. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.10854640 (**Data set**).
- [B8] A. Klingler, TMOR-jump. (Mar. 12, 2024). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.10810122 (**Software**).
- [B9] A. Klingler, 'About the transition phenomena of vitrimers a thermo optics and thermo mechanics perspective', presented at the Department of Chemistry and Chemical Technologies, TU Graz, Austria, May 27, 2024 (**Invited lecture**).
- [B10] A. Klingler, 'Thermo optical insights into the thermo mechanical behaviour of dynamic polymer networks (invited lecture)', presented at the Soft Matter Seminar, Martin Luther University Halle Wittenberg, Germany, Jun. 03, 2025 (**Invited lecture**).
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- [B13] A. Klingler, 'Personal blog documenting the state and progress of the Walter-Benjamin project funded by the DFG (2023 - 2025)'. [Online]. Available: <https://sites.google.com/view/andreas-klingler> (**Blog**).

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

- not applicable -